

Voltammetric Studies on the Reduction of Fe(III) at a Rotated Platinum Wire Electrode Using Different Surface States

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Reduction of Fe(III) has been studied using active and passivated surfaces of a rotating platinum wire electrode. The results obtained are found to be greatly influenced by the initial potential applied and the time for which the electrode is held at initial potential. The reduction is found to be reversible on a passivated surface, when I-V curves are recorded from +0.7V to 0.0V. Reversibility decreases appreciably when the curves are recorded from +1.0V. When reduction is studied using active surface the trend is reversed. The results indicate that platinum electrodes have a large number of surface states and each state influences Fe(III) reduction in its own way.

THE electrochemical reduction of Fe(III) at platinum electrodes has been the subject of numerous studies¹⁻⁹. A brief survey of the literature reveals inconsistencies in the results obtained by various workers. Most of the workers reported it to be an irreversible process, whereas Muller¹ had found it to be reversible. The poor reproducibility and diversity of results appear to be due to variations in the surface conditions of the electrode.

The platinum electrode surface has remained and is still a subject of vigorous research. Anson and King¹⁰ have classified these surface states and have described the techniques for controlling and altering surface conditions of an electrode. Chemical oxidation or anodic polarization of a platinum electrode in non-complexing media, such as perchloric acid solutions, produces platinum oxide film (oxidized platinum surface)¹¹⁻¹⁴. Oxidized surfaces can further be classified depending on the applied potential and the time of anodization¹⁵. Chemical or electrochemical reduction of an oxidized platinum electrode results in the formation of finely divided platinum metal on the surface (freshly reduced or active platinum surface). Several studies have demonstrated that, upon standing without reactivation the surface suffers a loss of its deposits of finely divided metal with resultant formation of an 'aged reduced platinum surface'¹⁶. In extreme cases aged electrode behaves as a stripped or bare electrode according to Anson and King¹⁰.

Hot nitric acid has been commonly used as an electrode cleaning material¹⁷. Such passivated surfaces have been well studied¹⁸⁻²¹, but their influence on the electrode reactions has still to be worked out. It appears that nitric acid treated electrodes, if used as such or after further anodization, can influence Fe(III) reduction. In this paper reduction of Fe(III)

on active and passivated electrode surfaces, which have been further exposed to different anodic potentials, has been studied. Necessity of further classification of the platinum electrode surfaces has been also examined.

Experimental

Instrument :

For recording current-voltage curves, an automatic photographic polarograph-System Heyrovsky LP55 was used. The scan rate was kept constant at 200 mV/minute.

Solutions :

All solutions were prepared from double distilled water, the second distillation being from alkaline permanganate. Ferric perchlorate solution was prepared by dissolving pure iron in the minimum quantity of 5M HClO₄. Other reagents used were of A. R. grade.

Cell :

A special cell (Fig. 1) made from corning glass was used. The main cell had a sub-cell within it. The sub-cell could be pushed in the centre of the main cell or held near the wall with the help of a position controlling rod.

Electrode :

The rotating platinum wire electrode (RPWE) was constructed by fusing a pure platinum wire of length 4.0 mm and diameter 0.75 mm at the lower end of a glass tube in such a way that the wire remained parallel to the axis of the tube. A Sargent synchronus motor was used for rotating the electrode

Fig. 1. Diagram of the cell.

at a speed of 600 rpm. Electrode connections were secured by filling electrode tube with mercury. All electrode potentials were measured against a SCE which was connected to the test solution through a sodium nitrate bridge.

Deaeration :

The test solution (always $2.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ $Fe(ClO_4)_3$ in $1M$ $HClO_4$) was taken in the main cell, whereas the sub-cell was half filled with the supporting electrolyte ($1M$ $HClO_4$). Solutions in both the cells were made free from oxygen by bubbling pure nitrogen through the solutions by a capillary tube (Fig. 1). During recording of the I-V curves the gas was passed over the surface of the test solution by holding the capillary well above the surface.

Electrode Surfaces :

Active Surface : The electrode was first boiled with nitric acid ($12N$ approximately) for about 5-10 minutes, then washed and boiled with double distilled water. After this cleaning procedure the electrode along with the salt bridge was inserted in the sub-cell and was successively cathodized at $-0.2V$ for about 5 minutes and anodized at $+0.2V$ for about 30 seconds to get rid of the adsorbed hydrogen. The surface so obtained was considered as reduced or active surface^{10,17}. The electrode and the salt bridge were pushed out of the sub-cell and inserted in the test solution for recording I-V curves. The use of the sub-cell enabled us to prepare the desired electrode surface outside the test solution, without letting it to come in contact with atmospheric oxygen.

Passivated Surface : In the first stage the treatment was similar to that for the active surface. Subsequently, in place of inserting the electrode in the test solution, it was taken out, washed with double distilled water and then stored in boiling nitric acid ($12N$) for 5 minutes. The electrode was then washed and boiled with double distilled water for about a minute and used as such. Further anodization of the passivated surface was also done in the sub-cell wherever necessary.

Temperature :

All experiments were carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ by immersing the cell and the reference electrode in a cryostat type MK-70, WEB MLW PRUFGERATE-WERK, (GDR).

The IR Correction :

The resistance of the cell as measured using Elico conductivity bridge was 1255 ± 45 ohms. The necessary correction for IR drop has been made in the reported values of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ and the slope. The correction, however, was minor and did not influence appreciably the shape of the I-V curves.

Results and Discussion

To facilitate discussion the following further classification of the two surfaces mentioned earlier is desirable.

(a) **Active Surfaces :** When $+0.6V$ was applied on an active Pt surface for half a minute the surface so obtained has been designated as $0.6A_{\frac{1}{2}}$ surface. To prepare the $0.6A_{\frac{1}{2}}$ electrode surface, the electrode with active surface was inserted in the test solution, $+0.6V$ was applied on it for half a minute and the curve was recorded from $+0.6V$ to $0.0V$. Similarly other surfaces such as $0.7A_{\frac{1}{2}}$ and $1.0A_{\frac{1}{2}}$ were obtained.

(b) **Passivated Surfaces :** With the same analogy passivated surfaces have been classified as $0.7P_{\frac{1}{2}}$, $1.0P_{\frac{1}{2}}$, $1.0P_{\frac{1}{6}}$ and $1.0P_{1.5}$ surfaces, where P stands for passivated surface, while the prefix figure stands for the initial applied potential, the suffix figure stands for the duration of the initial applied potential in minutes.

Initially applied potentials for durations longer than half a minute were applied in the sub-cell only. For example, for preparing $1.0P_{\frac{1}{6}}$ electrode surface the electrode with passivated surface was inserted in the sub-cell and $+1.0V$ was initially applied for 4.5 minutes. The electrode was then pushed out of the subcell and inserted in the test solution. The potential of $+1.0V$ was applied for a further duration of half a minute and the curve was recorded from $+1.0V$ to $0.0V$.

1. Active Surfaces :

A typical I-V curve obtained by using $0.6A_{\frac{1}{2}}$ surface is shown in Fig. 2(b). It is clear that $0.6A_{\frac{1}{2}}$ surface gives on ill-defined, drawn out wave indicating that the electron transfer process during

Fe(III) reduction is hindered at this surface. Previous workers have reported that in 1M HClO₄ no oxidation of platinum takes place upto nearly +0.52V vs SCE and that at +0.6V the electrode is oxidized reversibly to a small extent^{1,5}. The oxide is reduced immediately on starting the cathodic scan. Thus it is reasonable to assume that under conditions mentioned above the reduction of Fe(III) occurs on the active surface on which there is no adsorbed oxygen.

The curve 'c' in Fig. 2 is an example of Fe(III) reduction in which the voltage scan was started from +0.7V (0.7A_{1/2} surface). The curve, although not very well defined, does indicate a limiting current region with the following characteristics :

$E_{1/2}$ in volts vs. SCE	I_1 in μA	Slope of log plot analysis in volts
0.397 ± 0.007	3.48 ± 0.48	0.185 ± 0.008

Fig. 2. I-V curves for $2.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ Fe(III) reduction at : (b) $0.6A_{1/2}$ surface ; (c) $0.7A_{1/2}$ surface ; (a) Residual current (1M HClO₄) at $0.6A_{1/2}$ surface.

Recently it has been claimed by Johnson and Resnic⁹ that the adsorption of chloride ions, present in trace level as impurity facilitates the reduction of iron. If this was so adsorption should have been more pronounced on $0.6A_{1/2}$ surface than $0.7A_{1/2}$ surface and consequently the reduction should have been facilitated at $0.6A_{1/2}$ surface, which is not so.

At $1.0A_{1/2}$ surface double wave was obtained during Fe(III) reduction. A typical curve is given in Fig. 3(b). The pre-wave and the main wave have the following characteristics :

Wave	$E_{1/2}$ in volts vs. SCE	I_1 in μA	Slope of log plot analysis in volts
Pre-wave	$0.630 \pm .001$	1.51 ± 0.15	$.089 \pm .010$
Main-wave	$0.451 \pm .003$	4.28 ± 0.98	$.074 \pm .015$

Fig. 3. I-V curves for $2.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ Fe(III) reduction at : (b) $1.0A_{1/2}$ surface ; (a) Residual current (1M HClO₄) at $1.0A_{1/2}$ surface.

Hoare^{2,2} reported standard electrode potential for Pt/Pt-O couple as +0.88V vs. NHE (0.639V vs. SCE). The value agrees strikingly with the experimental $E_{1/2}$ value of the pre-wave. It is therefore reasonable to assume that the pre-wave observed at $1.0A_{1/2}$ surface is due to the reduction of platinum oxide formed earlier on the surface.

Anson⁴ has reported that the entire oxide film on the platinum electrode surface is not immediately reduced at $E < 0.5V$ and this remaining film is responsible for the observed irreversibility of Fe(III) reduction. It appears on comparing Figs. 3(a) and 3(b) that a peak due to surface oxide reduction occurs in the residual current curve and continues in the potential region of Fe(III) reduction. The presence of oxide layer is thus confirmed by our observations. However, it appears from the nature of the second wave that the reduction of Fe(III) is not hindered by the remaining oxide layer. Kolthoff and Nightingale³ have also concluded that the presence of oxide layer facilitates the reduction of Fe(III).

2. Passivated Surfaces :

Some observations on passivated surface are given in Fig. 4 and their characteristics are given below :

Surface	$E_{1/2}$ in volts vs. SCE	I_1 in μA	Slope of log plot analysis in volts
$0.7P_{1/2}$	$0.525 \pm .004$	4.18 ± 0.18	$.059 \pm .001$
$1.0P_{1/2}$	$0.503 \pm .005$	5.60 ± 0.60	$.067 \pm .002$
$1.0P_s$	$0.508 \pm .005$	5.05 ± 0.40	$.071 \pm .002$
$1.0P_{1s}$	$0.504 \pm .007$	4.70 ± 0.30	$.077 \pm .002$

It is apparent that reversible reduction of Fe(III) is obtained at $0.7P_{\frac{1}{2}}$ surface. The results favour the observations of Hoare, Thacker and Wiese²¹ about passivated platinum electrode surface. The transition from $0.7P_{\frac{1}{2}}$ to $1.0P_{\frac{1}{2}}$ is remarkable (appreciable irreversibility is observed). It seems that a significant change in the Pt-O alloy structure²⁰ takes place when the value of the impressed potential is changed from +0.7V to 1.0V. At 1.0P surfaces a slow but continuous movement towards irreversibility with increasing exposure time is observed. It may probably be due to a significant change in Pt-O alloy structure at +1.0V in the first few seconds, which continues slowly with time.

In contrast to I-V curves observed on $1.0A_{\frac{1}{2}}$ surface, which are always associated with a pre-wave, reduction of Fe(III) on 1.0P surfaces occurs as a well defined single wave. When $1.0A_{\frac{1}{2}}$ surface was replaced by $1.0P_{\frac{1}{2}}$ surface the oxide reduction peak occurring in the residual current, shifted within the potential region of Fe(III) reduction [compare Fig. 3(a) and 4(a)]. Thus only a single wave is observed on the passivated surface.

Fig. 4. I-V curves for $2.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ Fe(III) reduction at : (b) $0.7P_{\frac{1}{2}}$ surface ; (c) $1.0P_{\frac{1}{2}}$ surface ; (d) $1.0P_{\frac{1}{2}}$ surface ; (a) Residual current ($1M HClO_4$) at $1.0P_{\frac{1}{2}}$ surface.

I-V curves obtained using passivated surfaces are generally associated with maxima (Fig. 5). The phenomenon is related with surface condition, since no such maxima are observed when active surfaces are employed.

The limiting current observed for the constant Fe(III) concentration and rotation rate at passivated surfaces is generally high. This may be due to reduction of oxide layer along with Fe(III). Further investigations in this direction using other voltammetric techniques is in progress.

Fig. 5. Maxima as observed in the I-V curves for $2.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ Fe(III) reduction at passivated surfaces : (a) $0.7P_{\frac{1}{2}}$ surface ; (b) $1.0P_{\frac{1}{2}}$ surface.

Results obtained for Fe(III) reduction using $0.6A_{\frac{1}{2}}$, $0.7A_{\frac{1}{2}}$, $1.0A_{\frac{1}{2}}$, $0.7P_{\frac{1}{2}}$, $1.0P_{\frac{1}{2}}$, $1.0P_{\frac{1}{2}}$ and $1.0P_{1.5}$ surfaces show that these surfaces are essentially different from each other, though the difference between $1.0P_{\frac{1}{2}}$, $1.0P_{\frac{1}{2}}$ and $1.0P_{1.5}$ surfaces is not significant. The $0.6A_{\frac{1}{2}}$ surface gives an ill defined wave, whereas a pre-wave appears on $1.0A_{\frac{1}{2}}$ surface. The $1.0P_{\frac{1}{2}}$ and $1.0P_{1.5}$ surfaces requires much time for preparation without giving a significant difference from $1.0P_{\frac{1}{2}}$ surface. Thus we find that reproducible results can be obtained using $0.7A_{\frac{1}{2}}$, $0.7P_{\frac{1}{2}}$ and $1.0P_{\frac{1}{2}}$ surfaces. The Fe(III) reduction is most irreversible on $0.7A_{\frac{1}{2}}$ surface whereas reversible reduction is possible on a $0.7P_{\frac{1}{2}}$ surface.

Studies on other surface states with different parameters is in progress.

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